

Designed from Biobased Materials for Recycling: Imine-Based Covalent Adaptable Networks

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Turning thermosets into fully sustainable materials requires utilization of biobased raw materials and design for easy recyclability. Here, dynamic covalent chemistry for fabrication of covalent adaptable networks (CANs) could be an enabling tool. CAN thermosets ideally combine the positive material properties of thermosets with thermal recyclability of linear thermoplastics. Among the dynamic covalent bonds, imine bond, also called Schiff base, can participate in both dissociative and associative pathways. This induces potential for chemical recyclability, thermal reprocessability and self-healing. This review presents an overview of the current research front of biobased thermosets fabricated by Schiff base chemistry. The discussed materials are categorized on the basis of the employed biobased components. The chemical approaches for the synthesis and curing of the resins, as well as the resulting properties and recyclability of the obtained thermosets are described and discussed. Finally, challenges and future perspectives are briefly summarized.

employment of petroleum-derived materials and the depletion of fossil resources. Dynamic covalent chemistry (DCC) was first introduced by Wudl and co-workers in 2002,^[3] while the term covalent adaptable networks, also known as CANs, was coined by Bowman and co-workers referring to crosslinked polymer networks exhibiting reversible bonds.^[4] Covalent bonds can be classified as dynamic if it is possible to reversibly form and break them under equilibrium control and under impact of a specific stimulus. To achieve the equilibrium conditions and not to lose the mechanical properties characteristic for thermosets, the reformation of the broken linkages should be on a time scale spanning from milliseconds to few minutes.^[5,6]

The bond exchange in CANs can typically occur by dissociative or associative mechanisms. The dissociative pathway is

1. Introduction

Thermosets are irreplaceable materials for a wide range of applications due to favorable mechanical properties, thermal and chemical resistance and dimensional stability.^[1,2] However, being characterized by a highly crosslinked structure, they are persistent and not easy to recycle as they cannot be melted and reprocessed, which is an environmental concern. The introduction of dynamic covalent chemistry and reversible bonds in the thermosets' design represents a promising solution for the realization of reprocessable, chemically recyclable and/or self-healing thermosets. Furthermore, when dynamic covalent bonds are combined with biobased monomers, sustainable thermosets can be produced, omitting also the concerns linked to the

characterized by a bond-breaking event resulting in the cleavage of the crosslinking points; the diffusion of the resulting segments, exhibiting active sites through the network and the generation of new crosslinking points by the reaction of these active segments with complementary reactive moieties. In the associative CANs, bond-breaking and bond-forming events occur in a single step rather than in discrete dissociation and association steps.^[7,8] Differently from their associative counterpart, the double-step nature of the dissociative pathway makes the instantaneous crosslink density of these materials strictly dependent on the value of the equilibrium constant between associated and dissociated crosslinking points. Furthermore, in some cases due to chain rearrangement phenomena occurring during the migration of the active segments through the network, dissociative CANs can exhibit different crosslinking densities before and after the reprocessing.^[7]

Focusing on thermo-responsive dissociative CANs, Scheutz et al. explained that the equilibrium between the dissociated and associated crosslinking points is a function of the temperature.^[7] Indeed, in exothermic reactions, a temperature increase, lowers the crosslinking density, promoting the dissociation of the crosslinking points and the migration of the active segments through the network. For some systems, when high temperatures (well above the glass transition temperature) are applied, the material can depolymerize, becoming a fluid. Upon cooling, a sol-to-gel transition can take place: the generation of new crosslinking points occurs and the materials can return back to the solid state. Concerning the thermo-responsive associative CANs, the

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crosslinks density is generally constant and they do not depolymerize during the heating process.^[7,8] Therefore, the viscosity of the associative CANs does not drastically drop at temperatures higher than the glass transition temperature, but it follows the Arrhenius relationship, making these networks more similar to the vitreous silica than to the thermoplastics.^[8] In tune with this aspect, these materials are also known as vitrimers^[9] and their thermo-mechanical properties are generally assessed by means of dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) and stress relaxation measurements.

A constant storage modulus at temperatures more than 100°C above the glass transition temperature, assessed by means of DMTA, suggests the lack of variations in the molecular weight of the segments between the crosslinking points. Concerning the stress relaxation analysis, it is generally performed to get indirect insights on the viscosity of the network. In these measurements, the sample is stretched at a constant temperature (different temperatures are tested) until a fixed length is reached and the variations of the elastic modulus are measured over time, according to the Equation (1):

$$\eta = \frac{1}{3} E' \tau^* \quad (1)$$

Where η is the viscosity, E' is the storage modulus, and τ^* is the relaxation time. If the storage modulus does not vary with the employed temperature, by plotting $\ln(\tau^*)$ as a function of $1/T$, a line, showing a slope proportional to the activation energy for a viscous flow, is obtained.

This dependence has generally been considered as an exclusive characteristic of vitrimers. However, as clearly reviewed by Elling and Dichtel^[8] and also confirmed by Zheng et al.,^[10] in many thermo-responsive dissociative systems, only a small degree of crosslink dissociation takes place during the reprocessing and, therefore, the materials can turn out to show both a limited stress relaxation behavior^[11–14] and a rubbery plateau of the storage modulus extending from the glass transition to the gel-to sol transition temperature, when the majority of the crosslinking points are dissociated.^[15–17] Therefore, in order to more accurately assess the CANs mechanism, it is useful to perform DMTA measurements to high temperature to observe eventual gel-to-sol transition; to consider thermogravimetric analysis to study the decomposition of the network and to analyze the behavior of the network in non-reactive solvents.^[8] Regarding the last point, associative CANs are expected to show resistance to the dissolution, due to their constant crosslinking density. On the other hand, dissociative systems are expected to dissolve since the broken bonds are more difficult to reform when the swelling of the system occurs, with a consequent loss of integrity of the network.

In recent years, several kinds of chemical bonds have been demonstrated to be endowed with dynamic properties, conferring to the resulting polymer networks features typical of CANs.^[6] Chemical reactions, such as aldol reaction^[18] and Friedel-Crafts reaction,^[19] have been demonstrated to be reversible, conferring to C–C bonds the characteristic of dynamic covalent bonds. C=C bonds can give place to dynamic covalent reversible reactions, such as Diels-Alder and Knoevenagel reaction.^[6] Transesterification reaction and alkoxyamine exchange are widely used DCCs involving C–O bonds^[6] and

S–S bond is also among the most employed dynamic covalent bonds.^[20]

Among the reactions leading to the formation of dynamic covalent bonds, Schiff's base reaction is acknowledged as an important click chemistry reaction. In this reaction, active carbonyl groups are condensed with various nucleophilic primary amine groups to form imine (C=N) bonds.^[6] The presence of these bonds confers to the polymer excellent properties such as stimulus responsiveness, recyclability and self-healing. In light of the high potential of DCC for the development of recyclable and reprocessable biobased thermosets, this review summarizes the strategies developed so far for the fabrication of biobased thermosets utilizing imine-based DCCs and on the properties of these materials (Figure 1).

2. Imine-Based Dynamic Covalent Chemistry

The condensation reaction between an aldehyde or a ketone and a primary amine is a well-known reaction forming imines. In the presence of water and especially under acidic conditions, the hydrolysis of the imine with the consequent reformation of the original functionalities can occur (Figure 2a). Besides this dissociative mechanism, two associative pathways, both based on exchange reactions, can take place in the absence of water: transimination (Figure 2b) and imine metathesis (Figure 2c).^[21] Transimination refers to the reaction of an imine with a primary amine to form a new imine and a new primary amine. Conversely, the metathesis pathway consists of the reaction between two imines to generate two new imines. The transimination pathway has been reported not to require the presence of a catalyst and to generally occur when an excess of amines is present, leading to the formation of amination intermediates.^[22] Imine metathesis can be accelerated by an organic base catalyst such as L-proline^[23]; however, it has also been documented that the presence of a minute amount of primary amine can accelerate this associative pathway under non-acidic conditions.^[24]

While the potential of imine bonds to undergo thermally driven associative pathways has been exploited for the obtention of thermally reprocessable thermosets^[25,26]; the hydrolytic instability of the imine bonds is generally considered as a drawback of the imine chemistry.^[27] Nevertheless, this property has also been exploited for the realization of chemically recyclable polymers.^[21,28] As an example, a recyclable and reprocessable polyimine network taking advantage of both the dissociative and associative imine pathways was reported by Taynton et al.^[29] It was demonstrated that the polyimine networks, formed from commercially available aldehydes and diamine and triamine mixtures, exhibited Arrhenius-like malleability and stress-relaxation behavior in response to a temperature increase. Furthermore, the networks also showed water-induced relaxation at room temperature, turning out to be chemically recyclable at room temperature. The malleability and fast stress—relaxation of the polyimine induced with the increase of the temperature was explained by imine metathesis reaction and transimination, respectively; while the fast water-induced stress relaxation was explained by the combination of the imine dissociative hydrolysis and the transimination induced by free amine functions. Besides water-triggered systems, organic solvents have also been evaluated for promotion of imine bonds exchange reactions. In this

Figure 1. Schematic overview of so far utilized structural units and fabricated biobased recyclable thermosets utilizing Schiff's base chemistry with imine bonds.

frame, Chao et al. developed a self-healable organogel with imine cross-linkers and demonstrated that the synergic effect of excess of primary amines and polar organic solvents can promote the transimination pathway.^[30]

In order to get more insights on the imine bonds associative pathways as well as on the effect of the monomer and network composition on the kinetics of the associative pathways, Schoustra et al. highlighted the effect of polar functionalities in the polymer networks on the imine exchange.^[31] The study revealed that the reaction rate of imine exchange could be enhanced (up to five folds) by the introduction of more polar components (i.e., ethy-

lene oxide) with respect to the introduction of apolar components (i.e., aliphatic carbon chains). In tune with this result, the glass-to-rubber and the rubber-to-liquid phase transitions turned out to occur at significantly higher temperatures for crosslinked polymer materials containing polar functions in their structure compared with those containing apolar components. Finally, from the analysis of the stress relaxation behavior of the networks, a gradual three-phase relaxation process was highlighted, mainly consisting of the chain redistribution within the polymer network, imine exchange on local level, and imine exchange after diffusion through the network.

Figure 2. Dynamic covalent imine bonds' pathways; a) imine hydrolysis, b) transimination, c) imine metathesis. The mechanisms were redrawn based on Chakma and Konkolewicz.^[21]

3. Vanillin-Based Resins and Thermosets

Vanillin is an interesting aromatic compound with aldehyde functionality. Furthermore, it is already produced industrially from lignin,^[32,33] making it highly interesting as a biobased precursor for imine/Schiff base chemistry and fabrication of CANs. As an example, several vanillin-based epoxy and polyurethane CANs have been reported.^[34–41] Generally, the fabricated CANs illustrated favorable mechanical properties, good thermal stability, self-healing properties thermal reprocessability and easy chemical recyclability, typically by simply placing the thermoset in acidic water.^[34,39,40,42–44] The glass transition temperature of the different vanillin-derived thermoset was highly influenced by the nature of the amine component and varied from 14 to 214 °C depending, e.g., on the aromatic content and crosslinking density (see **Table 1**). Furthermore, besides the density of the aromatic functions and the structure of the selected amine-monomers, also the architecture of the network played an important role for the final thermal and mechanical properties of the thermosets. This also affected the thermally driven exchange pathways. As will be described in more detail below, it was reported that the thermal reprocessing of vanillin-based polyurethane thermosets could occur through an imine bond cleavage and reformation pathway,^[34] differently from other vanillin resins for which single-step associative pathways were generally reported.^[42,43] Similarly, for vanillin-based epoxy thermosets the resulting crosslinking degree was significantly affected by the reactivity of the epoxy functions toward the curing,^[37,40,41] with consequences on the network architecture as well as the kinetics of the imine exchange pathways. Fabrication and properties of different vanillin-based CANs are discussed in more detail below.

3.1. Vanillin Resins without Epoxy-Functionalities

The synthesis of vanillin-based vitrimers through the reaction between a di-vanillin monomer and conventional di- and triamine crosslinkers, as schematically presented in **Figure 3a**, was reported in 2018 by Geng et al.^[42] As expected, with increased crosslinking density, both the glass transition and the maximum decomposition temperatures of the resulting polyimines increased, passing from 48 to 64 °C and from 348 to 368 °C, respectively. These results demonstrated the higher rigidity of the materials and the stability of the networks when subjected to temperatures significantly higher than the glass transition temperature, confirming the associative nature of these CANs. The thermosets also exhibited self-healing ability and reprocessability. Interestingly, after the reprocessing, the mechanical properties (tensile strength and elongation at break) remained at the same level compared to the original samples and, turned out to be proportional to the crosslinking density of the original samples. Finally, the possibility to chemically recycle the thermosets, by subjecting them to an acidic aqueous solution at 50 °C, was demonstrated. This was attributed to the reversible equilibrium of the dynamic linkages, which means that acidic conditions in water can induce the opening of imine bonds and the reformation of aldehyde and amine functionalities, according to a dissociative pathway.

Recently, Zhou et al. developed a series of polyimine vitrimers synthesized by condensation reaction between vanillin-derived dialdehyde and trialdehyde with aliphatic amines.^[43] As expected, thermal analysis documented an increase of the glass transition temperature with the increase of the crosslinking density and thermogravimetry proved a weight loss lower than 1% w/w under 200 °C for all the produced thermosets. This result, together with

Table 1. Biobased thermosets classified in terms of employed aldehydes and amines, characteristics of the structure and properties. Glass transition temperature (T_g) and mechanical properties (stress at break, σ ; elongation at break, ϵ ; elastic modulus, E) were determined by means of DSC and stress-strain measurements, respectively, unless otherwise specified.

Biobased aldehyde	Amine	T_g	Mechanical properties	Summary of the properties
Vanillin ^[42,43]	tris(2-aminoethyl)amine, diethylenetriamine ^[42] ; Priamine 1071, Priamine 1074 ^[43]	$T_g \approx 48-64^\circ\text{C}$ ^[42] ; $T_g \approx 8-32^\circ\text{C}$ ^[43]	$\sigma \approx 47-57$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 8-16\%$ ^[42] , $\sigma \approx 2-6$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 168-640\%$, $E \approx 1-5$ MPa ^[43]	Self-healing, reprocessable and recyclable thermosets
Methacrylated vanillin ^[45]	2,2'-(ethylenedioxy)bis(ethylamine); trimethylolpropane tris[poly-(propylene glycol), amine terminated] ether	$T_g \approx 25-31^\circ\text{C}$,	$\sigma \approx 13-22$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 2-8\%$, $E \approx 470-830$ MPa	Highly crosslinked network, reprocessable and recyclable thermosets
Vanillin ^[46]	Tris (2-aminoethyl) amine	$T_g \approx 35-45^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA)	$\sigma \approx 7-17$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 78-103\%$, $E \approx 353-1322$ MPa (from DMTA)	Self-healing, chemically degradable and recyclable thermosets containing imine and disulfide bonds
Vanillin ^[34,35]	m-xylylenediamine ^[34] ; cysteine ^[35]	$T_g \approx 36-59^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA) ^[34] ; $T_g \approx 52^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA) ^[35]	$\sigma \approx 16-25$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 89-450\%$, $E \approx 103-244$ MPa ^[34] ; $\sigma \approx 35$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 9\%$, $E \approx 525$ MPa ^[35]	Highly crosslinked, self-healing, reprocessable and recyclable thermosets
Epoxidized vanillin ^[47]	4,4-diaminodiphenylmethane;p-phenylenediamine	$T_g \approx 183-214^\circ\text{C}$	$\sigma \approx 61-80$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 3-5\%$, $E \approx 2114-2709$ MPa	Highly crosslinked and flame-retardant thermosets
Vanillin ^[48]	4,4-diaminodiphenylmethane; 4,4-diaminodicyclohexylmethane; hexamethylenediamine	$T_g \approx 87-178^\circ\text{C}$	$\sigma \approx 35-69$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 9-15\%$, $E \approx 1426-1925$ MPa	Flame-retardant, reprocessable and recyclable thermosets
Hexa-vanillin terminated cyclophosphazane ^[44]	triethylamine	For the carbon fibers composite: $T_g \approx 98^\circ\text{C}$	For the carbon fibers composite: $\sigma \approx 185$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 2\%$, $E \approx 19000$ MPa	Flame-retardant, recyclable thermoset employed for the production of composites
Epoxidized vanillin ^[37]	isophoronediamine (IPDA) and polyetheramine D-400	$T_g \approx 14-199^\circ\text{C}$	$\sigma \approx 2-64$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 8-248\%$	Thermosets with crosslinking density and mechanical properties depending on the IPDA content
Epoxidized vanillin ^[38]	m-xylylenediamine	$T_g \approx 89^\circ\text{C}$	$\sigma \approx 3$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 6\%$, $E \approx 2470$ MPa	Thermoset with self-healing reprocessable properties, showing high thermal stability
Vanillin ^[39,40]	Hexane-1,6-diamine ^[27] ; isophorone diamine ^[28]	$T_g \approx 87^\circ\text{C}$ ^[27] $T_g \approx 121^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA) ^[28]	$\sigma \approx 85$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 6\%$ ^[27] ; $\sigma \approx 60$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 3\%$, $E \approx 2565$ MPa ^[28]	Self-healing, reprocessable and recyclable
Vanillin ^[41]	IPDA	$T_g \approx 108-184^\circ\text{C}$	$\sigma \approx 55-81$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 2-4\%$, $E \approx 1660-4301$ MPa	Thermosets able to retain thermomechanical properties after several reprocessing cycles

(Continued)

Table 1. (Continued).

Biobased aldehyde	Amine	T_g	Mechanical properties	Summary of the properties
Vanillin ^[49-51]	m-xylylenediamine; 1,6-hexanediamine ^[49] ; 4-aminophenol ^[50] ; Methylcyclohexanediamine ^[51]	For the thermoset: $T_g \approx 83-96^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA) ^[49] For the thermoset: $T_g \approx 70^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA) ^[50] ; For the thermoset: $T_g \approx 131^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA) ^[51]	For the thermoset: $\sigma \approx 73-78$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 6.1-6.8\%$, $E \approx 1960-2390$ MPa ^[49] For the carbon fibers composite: $\sigma \approx 622$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 4\%$, $E \approx 19300$ MPa ^[49] ; For the thermoset ≈ 63 MPa, $\epsilon \approx 7\%$, $E = 1600$ MPa, For the carbon fibers composite ≈ 450 MPa, $\epsilon \approx 5\%$, $E \approx 13000$ MPa ^[50] ; For the thermoset ≈ 82000 MPa (from DMTA), For the carbon fibers composite $\approx 61000-79000$ MPa ^[51]	Resins employed for the production of self-healing and recyclable composites
Vanillin ^[52]	4,4'-methylene dianiline	$T_g \approx 30-66^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA)	$\sigma \approx 9-1017$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 6-117\%$	Self-healing and reconfigurable thermosets
Trinavanillinphosphate ^[53]	diethylenetriamine	$T_g \approx 41-76^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA)	$\sigma \approx 7-21$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 12-2800\%$	Self-healing and recyclable thermoset. Transition from soft to hard thermoset with the increase of imine bond content
Vanillin ^[54]	2,2'-(ethylenedioxy)bis(ethylamine)	$T_g \approx 57-69^\circ\text{C}$	$\sigma \approx 61-77$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 4-6\%$, $E \approx 2000$ MPa	Reprocessable thermosets with high tensile strength and solvent resistance properties
Epoxidized syringaldehyde ^[22,55]	3,5-diamino-1,2,4-triazole ^[22] 1,4-butanediamine ^[55]	$T_g \approx 204^\circ\text{C}$ ^[22]	$\sigma \approx 57$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 6\%$, $E \approx 3000$ MPa ^[22] ; $\sigma \approx 86$ MPa, $E \approx 4$ MPa ^[55]	Thermally stable, flame retardant and recyclable thermoset, ^[22,55] also endowed with antibacterial properties. ^[22]
Levulinic enzymatic hydrolysis lignin ^[56]	Hexamethylenediamine; 1,12-diaminododecane	$T_g \approx 191-209^\circ\text{C}$	$\sigma \approx 60-79$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 2-6\%$, $E \approx 1869-2804$ MPa	Thermally and chemically stable thermosets showing UV protection properties
Soy protein ^[57]	–	–	$\sigma \approx 58$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 3\%$, $E \approx 6375$ MPa	Slightly crosslinked thermosets
Soy protein ^[58]	Long chain polyimide polyamine compound	$T_g \approx 93-166^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA)	$\sigma \approx 18$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 138\%$	Tough and functional composite thermoset showing UV shielding properties
Furan dialdehyde obtained from fructose ^[59]	Dimeric and trimeric amine mixture (Priamine 1071)	$T_g \approx -10^\circ\text{C}$	$\sigma \approx 0.7$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 24\%$, $E \approx 4$ MPa	Self-healing and reconfigurable thermoset
Furan dialdehyde ^[60]	Polyetheramines	$T_g \approx -50-5^\circ\text{C}$ (from DMTA)	$\sigma \approx 0.2-1$ MPa, $\epsilon \approx 20-50\%$, $E \approx 1-4$ MPa	Thermosets showing high thermal stability, tunable mechanical properties and reprocessability

Figure 3. a) The synthesis of di-vanillin based resins through the reaction with di- and triamine molecules. Reaction scheme was redrawn based on^[42] b) Degree of degradation for vanillin-based polyimine vitrimers under the influence of different factors. Reproduced with permission.^[42] Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society. c) Images and proposed mechanism for the dissolution of UV cured vanillin-imine thermoset by immersion in hexylamine/THF solution. Reproduced under the terms of the CC-BY license.^[45] Copyright 2020, the Author(s). Published by American Chemical Society.

the linear correlation between the $\ln(\tau^*)$ and $1/T$ demonstrated the occurrence of imine metathesis during thermal reprocessing of the vitrimers. Even these thermosets were easily chemically recycled in acidic water, as illustrated in Figure 3b, where the degree of mass loss under the influence of different factors, i.e., acid concentration and temperature, is reported. Degradation was concluded to occur through a two steps process: 1) swelling of the thermoset in the acidic solution; 2) opening of the imine bonds

and simultaneous release of aldehydes and amines into the aqueous solution, with a consequent increase of the turbidity and formation of a white precipitate, ascribable to the poor solubility of the formed aldehydes in water. The degradation process enabled the recovery of the vanillin-based monomers, which were reused for the preparation of new materials through hot pressing. The reprocessed materials showed elongation at break similar to the original thermosets; however, the breaking strength turned out

to decrease. This was deduced to the fact that, differently from the imine bonds, other covalent bonds, such as C–C bonds, that were destroyed in the process were not restored.

Interestingly, the investigation of the stability of the polyimines in different unreactive solvents (such as toluene, CHCl_3 , THF) illustrated the occurrence of a sol–gel transition after immersion for 24 h. Due to the absence of water or catalysts of the dissociative pathway, the result was ascribed by the Authors to the imine bonds' dynamic exchange pathways. This explanation was also supported by Tao et al., who carefully demonstrated that films prepared of polyimine CANs could quickly transform into sol in CHCl_3 .^[61] In the investigated system,¹HNMR analysis excluded the presence of water in the solvent as well as the reformation of the initial aldehyde functions. Furthermore, by means of dynamic light scattering technique, the presence of nanoparticles in the formed sol was assessed. In conclusion, the loss of film morphology and the subsequent sol–gel transition were not the result of the imine bonds dissociation, but they are ascribable to a rearrangement of the crosslinking network due to a fast imine bond exchange pathway. Photocurable vanillin-based resins, containing dynamic imine bonds, were produced by Xu et al. with the final aim to obtain thermally reprocessable and chemically recyclable thermosets.^[45] The fabricated thermosets immersed in various solvents (i.e., ethanol, acetone, THF, DMF, DMSO, and 1 M NaOH) turned out to mainly remain intact, although in some solvents slight discoloration and weight loss were observed. This result can be explained by the robustness of the photo-polymerized network, able to preserve the film morphology. The crosslinking density, jointly with the high density of the aromatic units, were likely responsible for the stability of the network even in 1 M HCl aqueous solution. Chemical recycling of the thermosets was possible by immersing the samples in an excess of hexylamine/THF solution for 24 h (Figure 3c). This was explained by the ability of the amine functions of the hexylamine to induce exchange reactions with the imines of the network (transimination), with a consequent transition from a crosslinked thermoset to linear molecules (Figure 3c). Concerning the reprocessability, while no great differences, in terms of elastic modulus, stress and deformation at break, were registered between the original samples and the samples that had gone through one grinding and hot pressing cycle; a slight increase of rigidity was observed for films subjected to two cycles, possibly highlighting the presence of small amount of unreacted vinyl bonds in the original thermosets. Finally, the possibility to reduce the stress relaxation time of self-healing, chemically degradable and recyclable vanillin-based CANs were demonstrated by the introduction of multiple reversible covalent bonds (i.e., imine and disulfide bonds).^[46] In particular, the presence of the disulfide linkages in the network turned out to positively affect the stress relaxation time, which decreased with the temperature, in agreement with the Arrhenius equation, due to a synergistic effect of imine and disulfide bond exchange pathways.

3.2. Vanillin-Based Polyurethane Resins

Recently, vitrimer-like polyurethane (PU) synthesized from vanillin, castor oil, m-xylylenediamine, 4,4-dicyclohexylmethane diisocyanate (HMDI) and 1,4-butanediol (BDO) was presented.^[34] Two distinct products were produced and evalu-

ated alone or in combination to produce the final thermosets, according to the scheme reported in Figure 4a. Similar to the work of Xu et al. described above, the stability of the vanillin based resins (VAN-OH) in an unreactive solvent as well as the decomposition temperature were significantly higher than those registered for pure BDO based resins, due to the stable covalent crosslinked structure, the high crosslinking density and the presence of aromatic vanillin units linked by Schiff base. However, it is worth mentioning, that, while the network conformation was retained when the materials were immersed in apolar solvents; the contact with polar solvents (i.e., DCM and THF), caused some swelling phenomena to take place. Indeed, polar molecules were able to interact with the network, leading to an increase of the swelling ratio and dissolution of uncrosslinked segments.

As expected, the glass transition temperature of the networks, evaluated by means of DMTA analysis, increased with the increase of VAN-OH units, which conferred a conjugated rigid structure to the network and a consequent increase of the crosslinking density. In tune with this aspect, at temperatures lower than the glass transition temperature, the storage moduli of vanillin-based thermosets were higher than those of BDO based networks. However, with the increase of the temperature to above the glass transition temperature, a slow downward trend of the storage modulus was observed for VAN-OH thermosets. Conversely, BDO networks turned out to show a stable rubbery plateau. The reason of the different behaviors between the two networks lies in the different nature of covalent bonds present. The stress relaxation analysis confirmed the ability of VAN-OH thermosets to quickly undergo a complete stress relaxation at elevated temperature. Furthermore, pure VAN-OH thermosets turned out to behave as a fluid under a constant strain of 5% at high temperature (around 170°C). Taken together, the observed phenomena indicated the occurrence of imine bond cleavage and reformation pathways due to the metathesis mechanism, with a cutting of the crosslinking points at elevated temperature. The thermosets prepared from pure VAN-OH resin, were able to maintain their mechanical properties after three grinding-hot pressing cycles and they also exhibited self-healing properties. Indeed, after being completely cut in half, overlapping the two pieces and heating them at 160 °C for 30 min, activated imine exchange reactions resulting in welding of the thermoset pieces. Finally, the obtained imine-based PUs underwent rapid degradation in acidic solution due to the hydrolysis of the imine linkages, potentially enabling the recycling of the network.

Few years earlier, Lee et al. reported the realization of PU crosslinkers synthesized by Schiff base reaction between vanillin and cysteine.^[35] Thanks to the structure of cysteine, the crosslinker contained both imine and disulfide bonds resulting in mechanically recyclable thermosets (Figure 4b) with much faster stress relaxation behavior with respect to the samples containing only one kind of dynamic covalent bonds. This was explained by the synergic contribution of dual metathesis reactions of imine and disulfide bonds, as illustrated in Figure 4c.

3.3. Vanillin and Phosphorous Complex Based Resins

Vanillin and phosphorous containing compounds have been combined for the development of flame-retardant resins. In

Figure 4. a) Structure of PU-like resins obtained by the reaction of HDMI functionalized castor oil with vanillin-imine molecule (low) and 1,4-butanediol (up). The reaction schemes were redrawn based on^[34] b) Stress–strain curves of pristine and recycled polyurethane-vanillin-cysteine (SPU) thermosets. Reproduced with permission.^[35] Copyright 2019, Elsevier Ltd. c) Comparison of the stress-relaxation behaviors of PU-like thermosets having both disulfide and imine bonds with thermosets exhibiting only one kind of dynamic covalent bond. Reproduced with permission.^[35] Copyright 2019, Elsevier Ltd.

2017, Wang et al. produced such resins by coupling two vanillin molecules through a Schiff base reaction with diamine.^[47] The formed Schiff base intermediate reacted with diethyl phosphite leading to the formation of phosphorous with difunctional phenols. As a final step, epoxy resins were achieved by a reaction between phenol groups and epichlorohydrin and the resins were cured by using a commercial curing agent. As a comparison, thermosets produced from bisphenol A epoxy resin (DGEBA) were also characterized. The produced thermosets turned out to illustrate typical stress relaxation behavior of CANs: with the increase of the applied temperature, the reduction of the stress relaxation time took place, due to the occurrence of imine bonds exchanges. As expected, the networks containing flexible structures were characterized by the fastest bond exchange; while thermosets containing conjugated aromatic rings exhibited the slowest ones.

Flame retardancy properties were assessed by means of vertical burning test, which is the standard test to evaluate flammability of plastic materials in devices and appliances, and by limited oxygen index (LOI) examination. Differently from DGEBA thermosets, for which no rating and a LOI of only 24.6% were registered, the phosphorous containing thermosets satisfied a UL-94 V0 rating, which is the highest flame-retardant rating, and reached a LOI of around 32%. The outstanding flame-retardant properties of these thermosets can be ascribed to their good ability to form intumescent and dense char layers during the combustion, thanks to the presence of the phosphorous. Besides these promising properties, the new thermosets also exhibited, with respect to DGEBA thermosets, higher glass transition temperatures and tensile moduli, both ascribable to the higher crosslinking density and rigidity of the structure

containing aromatic rings and polar N-H intramolecular hydrogen bonds.

The same authors, in a successive work, reported the production of vanillin-based, but not epoxidized thermosets.^[48] In this work, besides demonstrating interesting material properties, mechanical reprocessing of the thermosets and chemical recycling with monomer recovery were also demonstrated. Concerning the mechanical recycling, grinded pieces of the thermosets were reprocessable at temperatures as low as 180°C. The chemical structure of the polyimine was preserved during the reprocessing and no significant decrease of mechanical properties was registered. Furthermore, the amount of formed bonds and unreacted aldehyde was not affected by the reprocessing temperature. With regards to the monomer recovery, the crosslinked thermoset was hydrolysable under mild acidic conditions. After the chemical recycling process, the majority of the imine linkages were opened and around 70% of the original aldehyde functions were recovered.

Liu et al. realized a resin with some similarities to the previously reported ones except for the use of hexa-vanillin terminated cyclophosphazane and triethylamine as resin components.^[44] The thermoset was demonstrated to be readily recyclable and exhibited excellent flame retardancy. It was also further employed as a binder material to prepare carbon fiber reinforced composites. The resulting composites displayed excellent reparability, due to the presence of dynamic covalent imine bonds, showing only a slight decrease of the registered flexural performance, which was explained by the damage of the carbon fiber layers close to the upper surface. Concerning the recyclability, the composites turned out to be completely degraded during 12 h at room temperature in an acidic solution. Interestingly, almost total recovery of carbon nanofibers and resin components was achieved.

3.4. Vanillin-Based Epoxy Resins

3.4.1. Vanillin-Based Epoxy-Imine Networks

Many efforts have been devoted to the development of biobased epoxy resins as alternatives to petroleum-derived bisphenol A resins. As already discussed among the possible biobased molecules, vanillin shows great potential, especially in light of its aromatic structure and the presence of attractive functional groups. Epoxidized vanillin, generally obtained by a reaction with epichlorohydrin, has been employed for the development of a wide platform of Schiff base epoxy resins, using primary amines as spacers.^[36,38,62–64] The achieved results documented the suitability of Schiff base di-vanillin monomers as alternatives to bisphenol A for the development of thermosets. Indeed, when cured with a commercial hardener, the resulting vanillin-based thermosets showed, in terms of mechanical properties, no great differences with respect to the petroleum-derived ones. The glass transition temperatures of these thermosets ranged from 80 to 200 °C,^[62–64] depending on the flexibility of the employed spacer between the vanillin units, the reactivity of the epoxy functions toward the curing agent and the presence of Schiff-base related hydrogen groups. Moreover, the aromatic structure of vanillin conferred these networks higher thermal stability with respect to the thermoset prepared from Bisphenol A. The stress-relaxation

analysis performed on these networks highlighted a reduction of the stress relaxation time with the increase of the temperature and an Arrhenius correlation between $\ln(\tau^*)$ and the inverse of the temperature.^[36,38,65] These results suggest the occurrence of a thermo-sensitive associative exchange of imine bonds,^[65] catalyzed by residual unreacted primary amine groups, or of an imine metathesis pathway,^[38] both endowing reprocessability.

The water-sensitive nature of imine bonds can also be exploited for the production of materials showing water-driven malleability. In this frame, Zhao and Abu-Omar reported an experiment consisting of immersing a thermoset film in water for 4 h at room temperature; then, the wet sample was stretched over a round-bottomed flask and placed in a vacuum desiccator until fully dried.^[36] The authors then demonstrated that the dried sample retained the new conferred shape, while retaining robust mechanical properties. It is worth noticing that, also for these thermosets, the dissociation of imine in water can be controlled by properly adjusting the crosslinking density of the networks as well as the structure of the employed diamine. Indeed, for highly crosslinked epoxy networks with aromatic spacers between the vanillin units, no hydrolysis reactions took place in water; while swelling and degradability could be achieved in the presence of polar solvents, which were able to penetrate the network and induce solubilization.^[38]

Mo et al., with the aim of obtaining further insights on the effect of the employed amine-containing molecules and curing agent on the resulting properties, produced a series of epoxy-imine thermosets.^[37] Resins were fabricated by mixing epoxidized vanillin with isophoronediamine (IPDA) and polyetheramine D-400 (D-400). In these systems, the primary amines were both involved in reactions with the aldehyde groups of the vanillin-molecule and in the formation of permanent knots with epoxy groups, giving place to the network reported in **Figure 5a**. Due to their respective structures, IPDA was expected to improve the robustness of the resin and D-400 to confer greater flexibility.

As expected, thermosets composed of only IPDA (100% IPDA), as amine-containing molecule, did not show a uniform crosslinking density, due to the rigid structure of IPDA which hampered the encounters of reactive groups. On the other hand, FTIR analysis reported that the higher the IPDA content the lower the intensity of the aldehyde absorption peak. This feature can be ascribed to the rigidity conferred by IPDA, which limited the permeation of water inside the network and, therefore also the hydrolysis of the imine bonds. Thermosets turned out to preserve their appearance after three recycling processes, except for the material 100%IPDA, which showed strain shrinkage, due to the incomplete curing before the reprocessing. Furthermore, FTIR analysis documented a weaker absorption in the region between 960 and 1300 cm^{-1} , which was attributed to the evaporation of IPDA during the thermal reprocessing.

In light of these results, some considerations for the choice of the curing temperature were summarized.^[37] High-temperature curing of the epoxy-imine resins might induce the evaporation of the curing agent and the occurrence of irreversible crosslinking reactions which can affect the acid catalyzed degradability of the thermoset. On the other hand, high temperatures can favor the formation of reprocessable thermosets showing high rigidity. Conversely, low-temperature curing can favor the

production of crosslinked epoxy-imine thermosets with susceptibility to degradation in acidic solutions, but it likely also leads to incomplete curing of the resins with high glass transition temperature, due to the poor chain mobility below glass transition temperature.

3.4.2. Vanillin-Based Hardeners in Epoxy Resins

A different strategy, with respect to the realization of vanillin-based epoxy resins, is represented by the use of vanillin-based hardeners forming Schiff base bonds to crosslink petroleum-derived or biobased epoxy resins. With the aim to confer recyclability to petroleum-derived commercial resins, hardeners obtained from the condensation between vanillin and diamines have been developed and introduced in the resin structure. The introduction of a hardener obtained by the reaction between vanillin and diamine units in a commercial resin has been reported to induce insolubility of the resulting networks in many common organic solvents (toluene, ethanol, dimethylformamide, dimethyl acetate), although swelling of the samples was observed in polar solvents.^[39] This is in tune with the results previously reported for vanillin thermosets not containing epoxy functions. Conversely, due to the hydrolysis of the imine bonds, a rapid dissolution was registered after immersion in slightly acidic solution. Furthermore, the thermosets turned out to be endowed with self-healing properties thanks to the occurrence of metathesis reactions, taking place at the interface of two overlapped samples.^[39,40] Similar to the vanillin-based epoxy imine networks, also these CANs showed a clear stress relaxation when heated, with a decrease of the relaxation time values with the increase of temperature. The phenomenon is linked to the exchange reactions between the dynamic covalent bonds and it is also affected by the crosslinking density of the cured epoxy resin.^[41] Indeed, for highly crosslinked CANs, the exchange mechanism requires higher activation energy, demonstrating the important role of the architecture of the cross-linked epoxy networks for the kinetics of exchange reactions between dynamic covalent bonds.^[40]

Commercial epoxy resins with vanillin-based hardeners, exhibiting Schiff base bonds, have also been employed for the realization of composites reinforced with carbon fibers.^[49] The composite resins, differing from each other by the employed diamine (m-xylylenediamine and 1,6-hexanediamine), were used for the fabrication of cured CF/VMP and CF/VHP thermoset composites, respectively. The results of the characterizations are schematized in Figure 5b. Both materials showed excellent mechanical properties with tensile strength, elastic modulus and elongation at break around 600 MPa, 18 GPa and 4%, respectively. The SEM cross-sectional analysis demonstrated that the fracture surface was neat, indicating good bonding of the fibers inside the ma-

trix. Furthermore, the polymeric component of the composites was easily solubilized under slightly acidic conditions, by exploiting imine bond dissociative pathway. This was confirmed by the changing color of the solution over time and enabled the recovery of the carbon fibers.

Liu et al., in a similar work, demonstrated the possibility to recover the carbon fiber fabrics by inducing the dissolution of the cured epoxy resin through an amine-imine exchange reaction between the amine functions of the solvent and the imine groups of the network. The process enabled to recover good quality fabrics, that were easily recycled, as shown in Figure 5c.^[50] Furthermore, a similar composite was also demonstrated to show self-healing properties.^[51] Indeed, thanks to the resin structure, the resulting matrix could be completely repaired after damage; in particular, the interlaminar shear failure was almost totally recovered by a hot-press treatment.

Although the introduction of vanillin-based hardeners containing Schiff bonds in epoxy-resins can solve the problem of poor recyclability and reprocessability, it is worth to consider that commercial resins as well as epichlorohydrin can be toxic for living organisms.^[66,67] Epoxidized vegetable oils (EVOs) represent a promising route for the development of biobased thermosets; however, their highly crosslinked structure coupled with rather flexible backbones can lead to thermosets characterized by poor rigidity, poor mechanical strength and low glass transition temperature.^[68] Recently, Zhao et al. proposed epoxy resins obtained by crosslinking epoxidized soybean oil with vanillin-derived Schiff base (VSB) as hardener.^[52] Different amounts of VSB were added to the resins with following phenol hydroxyl/epoxy equivalent ratios (R) ranging from 0.5 to 1. Resins, labeled VESOV-0.5, VESOV-0.6, VESOV-0.7, VESOV-0.8, VESOV-0.9, and VESOV-1.0, were obtained. The gel fraction measurements reported that the gel content of all the resins ranged between 84% and 91%. The highest value was reached for VESOV-0.7, demonstrating that $R = 0.7$ is the optimal equivalent ratio for obtaining highly crosslinked VESOV network. This is similar to the optimal R value for curing reaction between epoxidized soybean oil and dicarboxylic acids.^[69] In tune with the previously described studies, a decrease of the stress relaxation time was observed with the increase of the temperature to which the networks were subjected. Furthermore, the stress relaxation time turned out to be lower for the networks showing higher content of Schiff base units, confirming the relevant role of the imine bonds exchange on the network stress relaxation. The gel fraction of remolded VESOV-0.7 was in the range of 85–92%, comparable to that of original VESOV-0.7, which demonstrated the capability of the imine bonds to endow the cured resins with reprocessability and thermal recyclability without destroying the network structure. Furthermore, the presence of Schiff base units conferred weldability and reconfigurability to the thermosets, as documented in Figure 5d.

Figure 5. a) Vanillin-based epoxy thermosets obtained by mixing epoxidized vanillin with isophoronediamine (IPDA) and polyetheramine D-400 (D-400). The reaction schemes were redrawn based on.^[37] b) Images, representative stress-strain curves, SEM images and degradation test of composites obtained by combining carbon fibers with vanillin-m-xylylenediamine (CF/VMP) and vanillin-1, 6-hexanediamine (CF/VHP) thermosets. Reproduced with permission.^[50] Copyright 2021, under exclusive licence to Springer Science Business Media, LLC, part of Springer Nature. c) Recycling of carbon fiber composites in EDA solution. Reproduced with permission.^[50] Copyright 2021, American Chemical Society. d) Representative stress-strain curves of as produced and self-healed soybean oil-vanillin based epoxy thermosets (left) and pictures showing the thermal-assisted reconfigurability of the thermosets (right). Reproduced with permission.^[52] Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society.

Inspired by the structures of biomolecules, researchers have developed, over the years, polymers with H-bonds in their structures.^[70,71] As known, H-bonds are characterized by lower bond energies compared to covalent bonds and, therefore, they can readily dissociate when subjected to heat or external force. Song et al. used this approach to develop biobased thermosets, labeled TAESO, with both Schiff base and H-bonding. Trina-vanillinphosphate (TVP) was utilized as a hardener for epoxidized soybean oil, subjected to aminolysis and ring opening reactions with polyamine, in the main chain.^[53] The collected results demonstrated that, by increasing the imine bond content, the transition of the polymer from soft to stiff occurred. Since both imine metathesis and the association/dissociation reactions of H-bonds are sensitive to the temperature, TAESO exhibited self-healing and recyclability, with a complete recovery of the original mechanical and thermal properties after both processes.

A different approach for the development of biobased thermosets, with epoxidized functions and vanillin-derived Schiff base as hardener, was recently proposed by Snyder et al.^[54] The development of the thermosets started from the synthesis of a platform of low molecular weight epoxide/cyclic anhydride polyesters containing pendant vanillin molecules. A reaction was then induced between the aldehydes of vanillin molecules and the amine functions of diamines. The work represents a step forward with respect to the previously reported strategies, which mainly proposed the formation of resins by step-growth approaches from discrete small molecules. FTIR spectroscopy highlighted the high conversion of aldehydes and amines to imines; while the glass transition temperatures around 57–69°C, jointly with the brittle nature of the films, confirmed the high crosslinking density. For almost all the produced thermosets, DMTA analysis documented the presence of an extended rubbery plateau above glass transition temperature, consistent with a preservation of the crosslinking density during the occurrence of associative exchange reactions in the network. Furthermore, the dissociation pathway turned out to be triggered under aqueous or acidic conditions, leading to the regeneration of the starting materials. Finally, when reprocessed, the polyester imine materials exhibited quantitative recovery of their tensile properties and crosslinking density over multiple cycles.

4. Syringaldehyde-Based Imine Resins

With a chemical structure similar to that of vanillin, syringaldehyde is a phenolic aldehyde found in fruits, nuts, and plants that synthesize lignin-related compounds.^[72] Syringaldehyde has been investigated as a component for fabrication of epoxy thermosets with imine bonds. Nabipour et al. fabricated biobased epoxy thermosets by a reaction between syringaldehyde and 3,5-diamino-1,2,4-triazole, followed by epoxidation with epichlorohydrin.^[22] The thermal curing of the resins was performed by using a furan-based curing agent (DIFFA) derived from furfurylamine. A commercial DGEBA epoxy thermoset was also prepared as a comparison. The FTIR and ¹H-NMR spectroscopies confirmed the achievement of the chemical structures shown in **Figure 6a**. Tensile testing demonstrated that the biobased and petroleum-derived thermosets had comparable properties with tensile strength and elongation at break of 57 MPa and 3%, respectively. Differential scanning calorime-

try revealed a significantly high glass transition temperature of 204°C for the cured biobased thermoset, which was considerably higher than that of the fabricated petroleum derived thermoset (143°C). Additionally, the biobased thermoset displayed excellent flame retardancy properties with UL-94 V-0 rating and a LOI of 40%. Xie et al.^[55] confirmed that, when their syringaldehyde Schiff base network was subjected to combustion, a heat-induced self-crosslinking effect took place. This effect catalyzed the formation of a stable protective char, endowing the thermoset with excellent fire resistance properties. In accordance with the previously described works, the presence of imine moieties in the thermoset structure allowed fast recycling of the thermoset in acidic medium. Antibacterial properties of Schiff base materials in combination with lipophilic layers have also been demonstrated.^[73] Indeed, lipid-soluble Schiff base can easily enter in cell membranes, causing cell membrane breakdown and damage of DNA. In light of this, the antibacterial effect of produced resins was evaluated with help of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. As expected, the petroleum-derived thermosets did not show any antibacterial effects; while growth inhibition areas were detected around the biobased thermosets with imine bonds in contact with both bacteria, with greater inhibition areas in the case of *S. aureus*. These results can be explained by considering the presence of an additional peptidoglycan layer surrounding the Gram-negative bacteria which hampers the entrance of Schiff base to the inner membrane.

5. Lignin-Based Imine Resins

Lignin is the most abundant renewable aromatic polymer and the second largest biomass resource after cellulose.^[74] The chemical modification of lignin is indispensable for the fabrication of lignin-based polymers and, among the possible strategies, approaches exploiting the considerable content of –OH groups in lignin have attracted great interest. Recently, Huang et al. reported a novel fully biobased lignin derivative containing ketone functionalities. This derivative was obtained after reaction of enzymatically hydrolyzed lignin with levulinic acid through an esterification reaction.^[56] The obtained compound (labeled LEHL) was then reacted with diamines, leading to the formation of Schiff-base thermosets, the chemical structure of which was confirmed by FTIR. The fabricated thermosets showed a degradation onset temperature for 5% weight loss around 318°C and a residue of 36%. Interestingly, opposite to the majority of the biobased imine thermosets described so far good stability in acidic aqueous solution (0.1 M) with no degradation was demonstrated. This was attributed to the hydrophobic lignin and the aliphatic chains around the imine bonds in the polymer network, which significantly hampered the contact between water and the imine bonds. Also these lignin-derived crosslinked polyimines could not be remolded when hot pressed. This result could be ascribed to the high lignin content and slower reactivity of ketone-based imines compared to aldehyde-based imines, requiring higher temperatures and longer reaction times,^[75] which significantly hampered the occurrence of imine exchange reactions. Finally, the obtained thermosets exhibited excellent UV shielding properties, ascribable to the presence of phenylpropane structures in lignin molecules.

Figure 6. a) Scheme for the synthesis and curing of resins obtained from epoxidized syringaldehyde and furan-based curing agent (DIFFA) derived from furfurylamine. Redrawn based on the synthetic route presented in.^[22] b) Scheme for the fabrication of fully biobased resins by combining furan dialdehyde from fructose with an amine or a triamine derived from fatty acids. Redrawn based on the synthetic route presented in.^[59]

6. Protein and/or Carbohydrate-Based Imine Resins

Soy protein is a long chain macromolecule consisting of 18 different polar and nonpolar amino acids as structural units. The polar amino acids (i.e., cysteine, arginine, lysine, histidine) can be exploited for crosslinking to obtain resins with improved mechanical, thermal and water resistance properties. In 2013, Dastidar and Netravali proposed a sustainable approach for the production of soy flour (SF) thermosets.^[57] A three-step approach was followed: i) proteins from SF (PSF) were filtered and separated from the water-soluble carbohydrates (SFE); ii) sugars were converted to aldehydes and carboxylic acids in the presence of hydrogen peroxide; iii) oxidized SFE were used to crosslink PSF using Maillard chemistry. During the last step, aldehydes and carboxylic acids reacted with polar amino acids in PSF leading to the formation of imines, amides, esters and anhydrides. The occurrence of these reactions was confirmed by the changing color of the crosslinked protein, which switched from yellow to red. Differently from the non-crosslinked resin, the crosslinked resin remained almost intact after immersion in water for 3 days at 80 °C; however, slight degradation was observed jointly with a

low gel content of only 42% illustrating low degree of crosslinking. Another interesting work on the development of polyimine networks containing soy protein, was recently presented by Zhang et al.^[58] The network was obtained by mixing isolated soy proteins chains with a polyimine obtained by a Schiff base reaction between polyamide polyamine and dialdehyde starch. Compared with pure soy protein films, the resulting network was further strengthened by intermolecular hydrogen bonds that induced increased crystallinity, enhancement of thermostability and strength and robustness of the resulting films. Furthermore, the films demonstrated good water resistance, mainly ascribable to the formation of the numerous hydrogen bonds between the soy protein and the polyimine jointly as well as to the entangled structure of the network, which hampered the moisture absorption and diffusion. Finally, the resulting network turned out to be endowed with excellent UV shielding properties, ascribable to the cis-trans isomerization and intermolecular proton exchange of imine bonds.^[76]

Dhers et al. realized a biobased polyimine vitrimer that was totally composed of renewable carbon.^[59] The resin was produced by combining a biobased furan dialdehyde obtained from fructose with a biobased amine or triamine derived from fatty acids,

according to the scheme in Figure 6b. The successful polymerization was confirmed by FTIR analysis, which documented the disappearance of the vibrational band of aldehydes and the appearance of imine bonds in the analyzed films. Thermogravimetric analysis highlighted the thermal stability of the material, which showed a degradation onset at around 300°C. This indicated suitability for thermal reprocessing. The DSC characterization reported the presence of a glass transition temperature at -10°C, reflecting the flexibility of the material at room temperature. Although the glass transition temperature was low, the material turned out to be resistant to hydrolytic degradation (tested in aqueous neutral, basic and acidic conditions). This was probably due to the hydrophobicity of the employed amines. Full stress relaxation was achieved at a quite low temperature (80°C) in a short time (40 s) and also at room temperature in less than 1 h. Furthermore, the activation energy for the imine exchange reaction turned out to be relatively low (64 kJ mol⁻¹). These results can be ascribed to the high flexibility of the employed diamines, which were characterized by long carbon chains. Creep recovery experiments were performed by subjecting the sample to a constant stress of 2000 Pa for 1000 s, followed by a recovery time of 1000 s, in a temperature range between -10 and 40°C. The results highlighted that at temperatures higher than 0°C, permanent deformation of the elastomeric vitrimer occurred, due to the fast dynamic transamination exchange taking place inside the material.

More recently, an interesting study by the same authors investigated the properties of a family of furan-based polyimine vitrimers, differing in the crosslinking density and for the stoichiometric aldehyde-amine ratios used for their synthesis.^[60] As expected, higher crosslinking densities were obtained by increasing the amount of amine functionalities in the employed spacers; decreasing the spacers' molecular weight and employing stoichiometric amine to aldehyde ratios. The control of the relaxation time was achieved by acting on the crosslinking density, without the introduction of any catalyst. However, vitrimers prepared with an excess of amines turned out to show reduced relaxation times with respect to those showing stoichiometric aldehyde-amine ratios and similar crosslinking densities. This is attributed to the occurrence of a transamination mechanism between amines and imines in the network, which is characterized by a faster kinetic than the metathesis pathway. Differently from the previous study, all the prepared thermosets were completely dissolved in acidic aqueous solution due to the acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of imine bonds. Moreover, despite of the high crosslinking degree of some of the vitrimers, all of them completely dissolved in ethanol. ¹HNMR analysis of the solubilized thermoset in ethanol highlighted the absence of aldehyde functions and the presence of imine linkages. Therefore, in tune with Tao et al. (see Section 3.1),^[61] the result was not ascribed to the depolymerization of the system, but to its rearrangement into more soluble structures.

7. Summary and Future Perspectives

In recent years, significant progress has been made in the challenging field of biobased and recyclable sustainable thermosets. Here the dynamic covalent chemistry, such as Schiff base or imine chemistry, has appeared as an indispensable tool. The

majority of the adopted strategies combining imine chemistry and biobased raw materials utilized vanillin, a lignin-derived aromatic monomer, which thanks to the aldehyde functionality can form imine bonds with primary amines. Other investigated biobased resin components include syringaldehyde, levulinic acid, cysteine, lignin, epoxidized vegetable oils, proteins from soy flour, fatty acid derived amines and sugar-derived aldehydes and carboxylic acids, such as furan dialdehyde. Table 1 briefly summarizes the main characteristics of biobased imine thermosets presented in the literature and discussed in this review.

Dynamic imine bonds, thanks to their potential to give place to both dissociative and associative pathways, have been widely exploited for the development of malleable, self-healing, reprocessable and chemically recyclable thermosets. The studies reported and discussed in this review clearly document the sensitivity of the associative imine bond pathways to the temperature: the heating of the network induces the activation of the dynamic bonds exchange and a complete stress relaxation of the thermosets can be quickly achieved with a relaxation time that depends on the network's chemical structure and crosslinking as well as on the amine to aldehyde ratio. Indeed, highly crosslinked networks or thermosets obtained by using aromatic (di-)amines are generally characterized by slower relaxation times than thermosets presenting low crosslinking densities and long aliphatic segments in their structure. On the other hand, the high crosslinking density jointly with the presence of aromatic units inside the network have been demonstrated to prevent the dissociative pathway of the imine bonds in presence of water or moisture, conferring to the thermosets long-term stability toward hydrolysis. For these water resistant thermosets, the recyclability has been demonstrated to be achieved through immersion in strong polar solvent, eventually in presence of an acid catalyst, or in amine-containing solvents, in order to give place to the transamination pathway, with a consequent dissolution of the network. Alternative strategies to reduce the relaxation time of the network, without affecting its recyclability in aqueous environment, could be represented by the introduction of an excess of amine functions, in order to induce a metathesis exchange pathway, and the combination of several dynamic covalent bonds (i.e., imine and disulfide bonds), as recently reported.

Although biobased, self-healing and recyclable thermosets with promising properties have been demonstrated; some open questions still remain such as the stability of the imine thermosets toward hydrolysis, elevated temperatures or other environmental factors. Further investigations and understanding on how to design resins that can be cured to thermosets with good long-term performance under demanding conditions, at the same time as they retain easy chemical recyclability and/or thermal reprocessability. The potential compostability or (bio)degradability in natural environments is also yet to be studied. The existing results demonstrate the potential of Schiff base chemistry for fabrication of biobased and recyclable thermosets and the future will show whether these materials can be scaled-up to industrial products and reach properties that enable complete replacement of traditional fossil-based thermosets in our daily lives. Reaching this will require a multi-disciplinary effort from biotechnology and chemistry to material design and processing, engineering and life-cycle assessment to develop and confirm the

concept of sustainable thermosets and to promote their development at industrial scale.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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biobased and recyclable thermosets, dynamic covalent chemistry, imine bonds, Schiff base, vanillin

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